
Quaternionic Heisenberg-Robertson-Schrodinger and Maccone-Pati Uncertainty Principles

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Abstract: We derive quaternionic versions of Heisenberg-Robertson-Schrodinger and Maccone-Pati uncertainty principles.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Let \mathcal{H} be a complex Hilbert space and A be a possibly unbounded self-adjoint linear operator defined on the domain $\mathcal{D}(A) \subseteq \mathcal{H}$. For $h \in \mathcal{D}(A)$ with $\|h\| = 1$, define the **uncertainty** of A at the point h as

$$\Delta_h(A) := \|Ah - \langle Ah, h \rangle h\| = \sqrt{\|Ah\|^2 - \langle Ah, h \rangle^2}.$$

In 1929, Robertson [6] derived the following mathematical form of the uncertainty principle (also known as uncertainty relation) by Heisenberg in 1927 [4]. Recall that for two linear operators $A : \mathcal{D}(A) \subseteq \mathcal{H} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$ and $B : \mathcal{D}(B) \subseteq \mathcal{H} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$, we define the commutator $[A, B] := AB - BA$ and the anti-commutator $\{A, B\} := AB + BA$.

Theorem 1.1. [2, 4, 6, 8] (*Heisenberg-Robertson Uncertainty Principle*) *Let $A : \mathcal{D}(A) \subseteq \mathcal{H} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$ and $B : \mathcal{D}(B) \subseteq \mathcal{H} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$ be possibly unbounded self-adjoint linear operators. Then for all $h \in \mathcal{D}(AB) \cap \mathcal{D}(BA)$ with $\|h\| = 1$, we have*

$$(1) \quad \frac{1}{2} (\Delta_h(A)^2 + \Delta_h(B)^2) \geq \frac{1}{4} (\Delta_h(A) + \Delta_h(B))^2 \geq \Delta_h(A)\Delta_h(B) \geq \frac{1}{2} |\langle [A, B]h, h \rangle|.$$

In 1930, Schrodinger improved Inequality (1) [7].

Theorem 1.2. [1, 7] (*Heisenberg-Robertson-Schrodinger Uncertainty Principle*) *Let $A : \mathcal{D}(A) \subseteq \mathcal{H} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$ and $B : \mathcal{D}(B) \subseteq \mathcal{H} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$ be possibly unbounded self-adjoint linear operators. Then for all $h \in \mathcal{D}(AB) \cap \mathcal{D}(BA)$ with $\|h\| = 1$, we have*

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_h(A)\Delta_h(B) &\geq |\langle Ah, Bh \rangle - \langle Ah, h \rangle \langle Bh, h \rangle| = \frac{\sqrt{|\langle \{A, B\}h, h \rangle - 2\langle Ah, h \rangle \langle Bh, h \rangle|^2 + |\langle [A, B]h, h \rangle|^2}}{2} \\ &= \frac{\sqrt{(\langle \{A, B\}h, h \rangle - 2\langle Ah, h \rangle \langle Bh, h \rangle)^2 - \langle [A, B]h, h \rangle^2}}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

In 2014, Maccone and Pati derived the following uncertainty principles which work for orthogonal vectors [5].

Theorem 1.3. [5] (*Maccone-Pati Uncertainty Principles*) Let $A : \mathcal{D}(A) \subseteq \mathcal{H} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$ and $B : \mathcal{D}(B) \subseteq \mathcal{H} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$ be possibly unbounded self-adjoint linear operators. Then for all $h \in \mathcal{D}(AB) \cap \mathcal{D}(BA)$ with $\|h\| = 1$, we have

(i)

$$\Delta_h(A)^2 + \Delta_h(B)^2 \geq |\langle (A+B)h, k \rangle|^2 - \langle \{A, B\}h, h \rangle + 2\langle Ah, h \rangle \langle Bh, h \rangle,$$

$$\forall k \in \mathcal{H} \text{ satisfying } \|k\| = 1 \text{ and } \langle h, k \rangle = 0.$$

(ii)

$$\Delta_h(A)^2 + \Delta_h(B)^2 \geq |\langle (A-B)h, k \rangle|^2 + \langle \{A, B\}h, h \rangle - 2\langle Ah, h \rangle \langle Bh, h \rangle,$$

$$\forall k \in \mathcal{H} \text{ satisfying } \|k\| = 1 \text{ and } \langle h, k \rangle = 0.$$

(iii)

$$\Delta_h(A)^2 + \Delta_h(B)^2 \geq \frac{|\langle (A+B)h, k \rangle|^2 + |\langle (A-B)h, k \rangle|^2}{2}, \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{H} \text{ satisfying } \|k\| = 1 \text{ and } \langle h, k \rangle = 0.$$

(iv)

$$\Delta_h(A)^2 + \Delta_h(B)^2 \geq -i\langle [A, B]h, h \rangle + |\langle (A+iB)h, k \rangle|^2, \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{H} \text{ satisfying } \|k\| = 1 \text{ and } \langle h, k \rangle = 0.$$

(v)

$$\Delta_h(A)^2 + \Delta_h(B)^2 \geq i\langle [A, B]h, h \rangle + |\langle (A-iB)h, k \rangle|^2, \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{H} \text{ satisfying } \|k\| = 1 \text{ and } \langle h, k \rangle = 0.$$

(vi)

$$\Delta_h(A)^2 + \Delta_h(B)^2 \geq \frac{|\langle (A+iB)h, k \rangle|^2 + |\langle (A-iB)h, k \rangle|^2}{2}, \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{H} \text{ satisfying } \|k\| = 1 \text{ and } \langle h, k \rangle = 0.$$

(vii)

$$\Delta_h(A)\Delta_h(B) \geq \frac{-i\langle [A, B]h, h \rangle}{2 - \left| \left\langle \left(\frac{A}{\Delta_h(A)} + i \frac{B}{\Delta_h(B)} \right) h, k \right\rangle \right|^2}, \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{H} \text{ satisfying } \|k\| = 1 \text{ and } \langle h, k \rangle = 0.$$

(viii)

$$\Delta_h(A)\Delta_h(B) \geq \frac{i\langle [A, B]h, h \rangle}{2 - \left| \left\langle \left(\frac{A}{\Delta_h(A)} - i \frac{B}{\Delta_h(B)} \right) h, k \right\rangle \right|^2}, \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{H} \text{ satisfying } \|k\| = 1 \text{ and } \langle h, k \rangle = 0.$$

(ix)

$$\Delta_h(A)\Delta_h(B) \geq \frac{2\langle Ah, h \rangle \langle Bh, h \rangle - \langle \{A, B\}h, h \rangle}{2 - \left| \left\langle \left(\frac{A}{\Delta_h(A)} + \frac{B}{\Delta_h(B)} \right) h, k \right\rangle \right|^2}, \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{H} \text{ satisfying } \|k\| = 1 \text{ and } \langle h, k \rangle = 0.$$

(x)

$$\Delta_h(A)\Delta_h(B) \geq \frac{-2\langle Ah, h \rangle \langle Bh, h \rangle + \langle \{A, B\}h, h \rangle}{2 - \left| \left\langle \left(\frac{A}{\Delta_h(A)} - \frac{B}{\Delta_h(B)} \right) h, k \right\rangle \right|^2}, \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{H} \text{ satisfying } \|k\| = 1 \text{ and } \langle h, k \rangle = 0.$$

We are fundamentally concerned with the question: What are the quaternionic analogues of Theorems 1.2 and 1.3? We recall the definition of quaternionic Hilbert spaces.

Let

$$\mathbb{H} := \{a + ib + jc + kd : a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{R}, i^2 = j^2 = k^2 = ijk = -1\}$$

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be the skew-field of quaternion numbers with conjugation

$$\overline{a + ib + jc + kd} := a - ib - jc - kd, \quad \forall a + ib + jc + kd \in \mathbb{H}$$

and modulus

$$|a + ib + jc + kd| := \sqrt{a^2 + b^2 + c^2 + d^2}, \quad \forall a + ib + jc + kd \in \mathbb{H}.$$

Definition 1.4. [3] A left quaternionic vector space \mathcal{Q} over \mathbb{H} is said to be a (left) **quaternionic Hilbert space** if there exists a map (called as quaternionic inner product) $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle : \mathcal{Q} \times \mathcal{Q} \rightarrow \mathbb{H}$ such that the following hold.

- (i) $\langle x, x \rangle \geq 0, \forall x \in \mathcal{Q}$. If $x \in \mathcal{Q}$ satisfies $\langle x, x \rangle = 0$, then $x = 0$.
- (ii) $\langle x + y, z \rangle = \langle x, z \rangle + \langle y, z \rangle, \forall x, y, z \in \mathcal{Q}$.
- (iii) $\langle qx, y \rangle = q\langle x, y \rangle, \forall x, y \in \mathcal{Q}, \forall q \in \mathbb{H}$.
- (iv) $\langle x, y \rangle = \overline{\langle y, x \rangle}, \forall x, y \in \mathcal{Q}$.
- (v) \mathcal{Q} is complete w.r.t. the norm $\|x\| := \sqrt{\|\langle x, x \rangle\|}, \forall x \in \mathcal{Q}$.

We derive quaternionic analogues of Theorem 1.2 in Theorem 2.1 and Theorem 1.3 in Theorem 2.2.

2. QUATERNIONIC HEISENBERG-ROBERTSON-SCHRODINGER AND MACCONE-PATI UNCERTAINTY PRINCIPLES

Let \mathcal{Q} be a quaternionic Hilbert space and A be a possibly unbounded self-adjoint linear operator defined on domain $\mathcal{D}(A) \subseteq \mathcal{Q}$. For $x \in \mathcal{D}(A)$ with $\|x\| = 1$, we define the **uncertainty** or **variance** of A at the point x as

$$\Delta_x(A) := \|Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x\| = \sqrt{\|Ax\|^2 - \langle Ax, x \rangle^2}.$$

Given two elements $p, q \in \mathbb{H}$, we define the commutator $[p, q] := pq - qp$ and anti-commutator $\{p, q\} := pq + qp$. Similarly, for two maps $A : \mathcal{D}(A) \subseteq \mathcal{Q} \rightarrow \mathcal{Q}$ and $B : \mathcal{D}(B) \subseteq \mathcal{Q} \rightarrow \mathcal{Q}$, we define commutator $[A, B] := AB - BA$ and anti-commutator $\{A, B\} := AB + BA$.

Theorem 2.1. (*Quaternionic Heisenberg-Robertson-Schrodinger Uncertainty Principles*) Let \mathcal{Q} be a quaternionic Hilbert space. Let $A : \mathcal{D}(A) \subseteq \mathcal{Q} \rightarrow \mathcal{Q}$ and $B : \mathcal{D}(B) \subseteq \mathcal{Q} \rightarrow \mathcal{Q}$ be possibly unbounded self-adjoint linear operators. Then for all $x \in \mathcal{D}(AB) \cap \mathcal{D}(BA)$ with $\|x\| = 1$, we have

(i)

$$\Delta_x(A)\Delta_x(B) \geq \frac{|\langle [A, B]x, x \rangle + [\langle Ax, x \rangle, \langle Bx, x \rangle]|}{2}.$$

(ii)

$$\Delta_x(A)\Delta_x(B) \geq \frac{|\langle \{A, B\}x, x \rangle - \{\langle Ax, x \rangle, \langle Bx, x \rangle\}|}{2}.$$

(iii)

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_x(A)\Delta_x(B) &\geq \frac{\sqrt{(\langle \{A, B\}x, x \rangle - \{\langle Ax, x \rangle, \langle Bx, x \rangle\})^2 - (\langle [A, B]x, x \rangle + [\langle Ax, x \rangle, \langle Bx, x \rangle])^2}}{2} \\ &= \frac{\sqrt{(\langle \{A, B\}x, x \rangle - \{\langle Ax, x \rangle, \langle Bx, x \rangle\})^2 + |\langle [A, B]x, x \rangle + [\langle Ax, x \rangle, \langle Bx, x \rangle]|^2}}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let $x \in \mathcal{D}(AB) \cap \mathcal{D}(BA)$ be such that $\|x\| = 1$.

(i)

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta_x(A)\Delta_x(B) &\geq \langle Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x, Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x \rangle \\
&= |\langle Ax, Bx \rangle - \langle Ax, x \rangle \langle Bx, x \rangle| \\
&\geq \frac{|\langle Ax, Bx \rangle - \langle Ax, x \rangle \langle Bx, x \rangle - \overline{\langle Ax, Bx \rangle - \langle Ax, x \rangle \langle Bx, x \rangle}|}{2} \\
&= \frac{|\langle Ax, Bx \rangle - \langle Ax, x \rangle \langle Bx, x \rangle - \langle Bx, Ax \rangle + \langle Bx, x \rangle \langle Ax, x \rangle|}{2} \\
&= \frac{|\langle BAx, x \rangle - \langle Ax, x \rangle \langle Bx, x \rangle - \langle ABx, x \rangle + \langle Bx, x \rangle \langle Ax, x \rangle|}{2} \\
&= \frac{|-\langle (AB - BA)x, x \rangle - (\langle Ax, x \rangle \langle Bx, x \rangle - \langle Bx, x \rangle \langle Ax, x \rangle)|}{2} \\
&= \frac{|[\langle A, B \rangle x, x] + [\langle Ax, x \rangle, \langle Bx, x \rangle]|}{2}.
\end{aligned}$$

(ii)

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta_x(A)\Delta_x(B) &\geq \langle Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x, Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x \rangle \\
&= |\langle Ax, Bx \rangle - \langle Ax, x \rangle \langle Bx, x \rangle| \\
&\geq \frac{|\langle Ax, Bx \rangle - \langle Ax, x \rangle \langle Bx, x \rangle + \overline{\langle Ax, Bx \rangle - \langle Ax, x \rangle \langle Bx, x \rangle}|}{2} \\
&= \frac{|\langle Ax, Bx \rangle - \langle Ax, x \rangle \langle Bx, x \rangle + \langle Bx, Ax \rangle - \langle Bx, x \rangle \langle Ax, x \rangle|}{2} \\
&= \frac{|\langle BAx, x \rangle - \langle Ax, x \rangle \langle Bx, x \rangle + \langle ABx, x \rangle - \langle Bx, x \rangle \langle Ax, x \rangle|}{2} \\
&= \frac{|(\langle AB + BA \rangle x, x) - (\langle Ax, x \rangle \langle Bx, x \rangle + \langle Bx, x \rangle \langle Ax, x \rangle)|}{2} \\
&= \frac{|[\langle A, B \rangle x, x] - \{\langle Ax, x \rangle, \langle Bx, x \rangle\}|}{2}.
\end{aligned}$$

(iii) Define

$$z := Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x, \quad w := Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x.$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle z, w \rangle + \langle w, z \rangle &= \langle Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x, Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x \rangle + \langle Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x, Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x \rangle \\
&= \langle BAx, x \rangle - \langle Ax, x \rangle \langle Bx, x \rangle + \langle ABx, x \rangle - \langle Bx, x \rangle \langle Ax, x \rangle \\
&= \langle \{A, B\}x, x \rangle - \{\langle Ax, x \rangle, \langle Bx, x \rangle\}
\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle z, w \rangle - \langle w, z \rangle &= \langle Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x, Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x \rangle - \langle Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x, Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x \rangle \\
&= \langle BAx, x \rangle - \langle Ax, x \rangle \langle Bx, x \rangle - \langle ABx, x \rangle + \langle Bx, x \rangle \langle Ax, x \rangle \\
&= -[\langle A, B \rangle x, x] - [\langle Ax, x \rangle, \langle Bx, x \rangle].
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_x(A)^2 \Delta_x(B)^2 + \Delta_x(B)^2 \Delta_x(A)^2 &\geq |\langle z, w \rangle|^2 + |\langle w, z \rangle|^2 \\ &= \frac{(\langle z, w \rangle + \langle w, z \rangle)^2 - (\langle z, w \rangle - \langle w, z \rangle)^2}{2} \\ &= \frac{(\langle \{A, B\}x, x \rangle - \langle \langle Ax, x \rangle, \langle Bx, x \rangle \rangle)^2 - (\langle [A, B]x, x \rangle + [\langle Ax, x \rangle, \langle Bx, x \rangle])^2}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

Note that

$$\overline{\langle [A, B]x, x \rangle + [\langle Ax, x \rangle, \langle Bx, x \rangle]} = -(\langle [A, B]x, x \rangle + [\langle Ax, x \rangle, \langle Bx, x \rangle])$$

and

$$\overline{\langle \{A, B\}x, x \rangle - \langle \langle Ax, x \rangle, \langle Bx, x \rangle \rangle} = \langle \{A, B\}x, x \rangle - \langle \langle Ax, x \rangle, \langle Bx, x \rangle \rangle.$$

Therefore

$$-(\langle [A, B]x, x \rangle + [\langle Ax, x \rangle, \langle Bx, x \rangle])^2 = |\langle [A, B]x, x \rangle + [\langle Ax, x \rangle, \langle Bx, x \rangle]|^2$$

and

$$(\langle \{A, B\}x, x \rangle - \langle \langle Ax, x \rangle, \langle Bx, x \rangle \rangle)^2 = |\langle \{A, B\}x, x \rangle - \langle \langle Ax, x \rangle, \langle Bx, x \rangle \rangle|^2.$$

□

Next we derive quaternionic Maccone-Pati uncertainty principles.

Theorem 2.2. (Quaternionic Maccone-Pati Uncertainty Principles) *Let \mathcal{Q} be a quaternionic Hilbert space. Let $A : \mathcal{D}(A) \subseteq \mathcal{Q} \rightarrow \mathcal{Q}$ and $B : \mathcal{D}(B) \subseteq \mathcal{Q} \rightarrow \mathcal{Q}$ be possibly unbounded self-adjoint linear operators. Let $r \in \{i, j, k\}$. Then for all $x \in \mathcal{D}(AB) \cap \mathcal{D}(BA)$ with $\|x\| = 1$, we have*

(i)

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_x(A)^2 + \Delta_x(B)^2 &\geq |\langle (A + B)x, y \rangle|^2 - \langle \{A, B\}x, x \rangle + 2\langle Ax, x \rangle \langle Bx, x \rangle, \\ &\quad \forall y \in \mathcal{Q} \text{ satisfying } \|y\| \leq 1 \text{ and } \langle x, y \rangle = 0. \end{aligned}$$

(ii)

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_x(A)^2 + \Delta_x(B)^2 &\geq |\langle (A - B)x, y \rangle|^2 + \langle \{A, B\}x, x \rangle - 2\langle Ax, x \rangle \langle Bx, x \rangle, \\ &\quad \forall y \in \mathcal{Q} \text{ satisfying } \|y\| \leq 1 \text{ and } \langle x, y \rangle = 0. \end{aligned}$$

(iii)

$$\Delta_x(A)^2 + \Delta_x(B)^2 \geq \frac{|\langle (A + B)x, y \rangle|^2 + |\langle (A - B)x, y \rangle|^2}{2}, \quad \forall y \in \mathcal{Q} \text{ satisfying } \|y\| \leq 1 \text{ and } \langle x, y \rangle = 0.$$

(iv)

$$\Delta_x(A)^2 + \Delta_x(B)^2 \geq -r\langle [A, B]x, x \rangle + |\langle (A + rB)x, y \rangle|^2, \quad \forall y \in \mathcal{Q} \text{ satisfying } \|y\| \leq 1 \text{ and } \langle x, y \rangle = 0.$$

(v)

$$\Delta_x(A)^2 + \Delta_x(B)^2 \geq r\langle [A, B]x, x \rangle + |\langle (A - rB)x, y \rangle|^2, \quad \forall y \in \mathcal{Q} \text{ satisfying } \|y\| \leq 1 \text{ and } \langle x, y \rangle = 0.$$

(vi)

$$\Delta_x(A)^2 + \Delta_x(B)^2 \geq \frac{|\langle (A + rB)x, y \rangle|^2 + |\langle (A - rB)x, y \rangle|^2}{2}, \quad \forall y \in \mathcal{Q} \text{ satisfying } \|y\| \leq 1 \text{ and } \langle x, y \rangle = 0.$$

(vii)

$$\Delta_x(A)\Delta_x(B) \geq \frac{-r\langle[A, B]x, x\rangle}{2 - \left| \left\langle \left(\frac{A}{\Delta_x(A)} + r \frac{B}{\Delta_x(B)} \right) x, y \right\rangle \right|^2}, \quad \forall y \in \mathcal{Q} \text{ satisfying } \|y\| \leq 1 \text{ and } \langle x, y \rangle = 0.$$

(viii)

$$\Delta_x(A)\Delta_x(B) \geq \frac{r\langle[A, B]x, x\rangle}{2 - \left| \left\langle \left(\frac{A}{\Delta_x(A)} - r \frac{B}{\Delta_x(B)} \right) x, y \right\rangle \right|^2}, \quad \forall y \in \mathcal{Q} \text{ satisfying } \|y\| \leq 1 \text{ and } \langle x, y \rangle = 0.$$

(ix)

$$\Delta_x(A)\Delta_x(B) \geq \frac{2\langle Ax, x \rangle \langle Bx, x \rangle - \langle \{A, B\}x, x \rangle}{2 - \left| \left\langle \left(\frac{A}{\Delta_x(A)} + \frac{B}{\Delta_x(B)} \right) x, y \right\rangle \right|^2}, \quad \forall y \in \mathcal{Q} \text{ satisfying } \|y\| \leq 1 \text{ and } \langle x, y \rangle = 0.$$

(x)

$$\Delta_x(A)\Delta_x(B) \geq \frac{-2\langle Ax, x \rangle \langle Bx, x \rangle + \langle \{A, B\}x, x \rangle}{2 - \left| \left\langle \left(\frac{A}{\Delta_x(A)} - \frac{B}{\Delta_x(B)} \right) x, y \right\rangle \right|^2}, \quad \forall y \in \mathcal{Q} \text{ satisfying } \|y\| \leq 1 \text{ and } \langle x, y \rangle = 0.$$

Proof. Let $x \in \mathcal{D}(AB) \cap \mathcal{D}(BA)$ with $\|x\| = 1$. Let $y \in \mathcal{Q}$ be such that $\|y\| \leq 1$ and $\langle x, y \rangle = 0$.

(i)

$$\begin{aligned} |\langle (A+B)x, y \rangle|^2 &= |\langle Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x + Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x, y \rangle|^2 \\ &\leq \|y\|^2 \langle (Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x) + (Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x), (Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x) + (Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x) \rangle \\ &\leq \langle Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x, Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x \rangle + \langle Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x, Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x \rangle \\ &\quad + \langle Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x, Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x \rangle + \langle Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x, Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x \rangle \\ &= \Delta_x(A)^2 + \Delta_x(B)^2 + \langle Bx, Ax \rangle - \langle Bx, x \rangle \langle Ax, x \rangle + \langle Ax, Bx \rangle - \langle Ax, x \rangle \langle Bx, x \rangle \\ &= \Delta_x(A)^2 + \Delta_x(B)^2 + \langle \{A, B\}x, x \rangle - \{ \langle Ax, x \rangle, \langle Bx, x \rangle \}. \end{aligned}$$

(ii) Similar to (i).

(iii) We get by adding (i) and (ii).

(iv)

$$\begin{aligned} |\langle (A+rB)x, y \rangle|^2 &= |\langle Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x + r(Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x), y \rangle|^2 \\ &\leq \|y\|^2 \langle (Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x) + r(Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x), (Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x) + r(Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x) \rangle \\ &\leq \langle Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x, Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x \rangle + \langle Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x, Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x \rangle \\ &\quad + r\langle Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x, Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x \rangle - r\langle Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x, Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x \rangle \\ &= \Delta_x(A)^2 + \Delta_x(B)^2 + r(\langle Bx, Ax \rangle - \langle Bx, x \rangle \langle Ax, x \rangle) - r(\langle Ax, Bx \rangle - \langle Ax, x \rangle \langle Bx, x \rangle) \\ &= \Delta_x(A)^2 + \Delta_x(B)^2 + r\langle[A, B]x, x\rangle + r\langle Ax, x \rangle, \langle Bx, x \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$\Delta_x(A)^2 + \Delta_x(B)^2 \geq -r\langle[A, B]x, x\rangle + \langle (A+rB)x, y \rangle \langle y, (A+rB)x \rangle - r\langle Ax, x \rangle, \langle Bx, x \rangle.$$

(v) Similar to (iv).

(vi) We get by adding (iv) and (v).

(vii)

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \left\langle \left(\frac{A}{\Delta_x(A)} + \frac{rB}{\Delta_x(B)} \right) x, y \right\rangle \right|^2 = \left| \left\langle \frac{Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x}{\Delta_x(A)} + \frac{r(Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x)}{\Delta_x(B)}, y \right\rangle \right|^2 \\
 & \leq \|y\|^2 \left\langle \frac{Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x}{\Delta_x(A)} + \frac{r(Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x)}{\Delta_x(B)}, \frac{Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x}{\Delta_x(A)} + \frac{r(Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x)}{\Delta_x(B)} \right\rangle \\
 & \leq \left\langle \frac{Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x}{\Delta_x(A)}, \frac{Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x}{\Delta_x(A)} \right\rangle + \left\langle \frac{Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x}{\Delta_x(B)}, \frac{Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x}{\Delta_x(B)} \right\rangle \\
 & \quad + r \left\langle \frac{Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x}{\Delta_x(B)}, \frac{Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x}{\Delta_x(A)} \right\rangle - r \left\langle \frac{Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x}{\Delta_x(A)}, \frac{Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x}{\Delta_x(B)} \right\rangle \\
 & = 1 + 1 + \frac{r \langle Bx, Ax \rangle - r \langle Bx, x \rangle \langle Ax, x \rangle}{\Delta_x(A) \Delta_x(B)} + \frac{-r \langle Ax, Bx \rangle + r \langle Ax, x \rangle \langle Bx, x \rangle}{\Delta_x(A) \Delta_x(B)} \\
 & = 2 + \frac{r \langle [A, B] x, x \rangle}{\Delta_x(A) \Delta_x(B)}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{-r \langle [A, B] x, x \rangle}{\Delta_x(A) \Delta_x(B)} & \leq 2 - \left| \left\langle \left(\frac{A}{\Delta_x(A)} + \frac{rB}{\Delta_x(B)} \right) x, y \right\rangle \right|^2 \\
 \implies \frac{-r \langle [A, B] x, x \rangle}{2 - \left| \left\langle \left(\frac{A}{\Delta_x(A)} + \frac{rB}{\Delta_x(B)} \right) x, y \right\rangle \right|^2} & \leq \Delta_x(A) \Delta_x(B).
 \end{aligned}$$

(viii) Similar to (vii).

(ix)

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \left\langle \left(\frac{A}{\Delta_x(A)} + \frac{B}{\Delta_x(B)} \right) x, y \right\rangle \right|^2 = \left| \left\langle \frac{Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x}{\Delta_x(A)} + \frac{Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x}{\Delta_x(B)}, y \right\rangle \right|^2 \\
 & \leq \|y\|^2 \left\langle \frac{Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x}{\Delta_x(A)} + \frac{Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x}{\Delta_x(B)}, \frac{Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x}{\Delta_x(A)} + \frac{Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x}{\Delta_x(B)} \right\rangle \\
 & \leq \left\langle \frac{Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x}{\Delta_x(A)}, \frac{Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x}{\Delta_x(A)} \right\rangle + \left\langle \frac{Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x}{\Delta_x(B)}, \frac{Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x}{\Delta_x(B)} \right\rangle \\
 & \quad + \left\langle \frac{Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x}{\Delta_x(B)}, \frac{Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x}{\Delta_x(A)} \right\rangle + \left\langle \frac{Ax - \langle Ax, x \rangle x}{\Delta_x(A)}, \frac{Bx - \langle Bx, x \rangle x}{\Delta_x(B)} \right\rangle \\
 & = 1 + 1 + \frac{\langle Bx, Ax \rangle - \langle Bx, x \rangle \langle Ax, x \rangle}{\Delta_x(A) \Delta_x(B)} + \frac{\langle Ax, Bx \rangle - \langle Ax, x \rangle \langle Bx, x \rangle}{\Delta_x(A) \Delta_x(B)} \\
 & = 2 + \frac{2 \langle Ax, x \rangle \langle Bx, x \rangle + \langle \{A, B\} x, x \rangle}{\Delta_x(A) \Delta_x(B)}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned}
 -\frac{-2 \langle Ax, x \rangle \langle Bx, x \rangle + \langle \{A, B\} x, x \rangle}{\Delta_x(A) \Delta_x(B)} & \leq 2 - \left| \left\langle \left(\frac{A}{\Delta_x(A)} + \frac{B}{\Delta_x(B)} \right) x, y \right\rangle \right|^2 \\
 \implies \frac{2 \langle Ax, x \rangle \langle Bx, x \rangle - \langle \{A, B\} x, x \rangle}{2 - \left| \left\langle \left(\frac{A}{\Delta_x(A)} + \frac{B}{\Delta_x(B)} \right) x, y \right\rangle \right|^2} & \leq \Delta_x(A) \Delta_x(B).
 \end{aligned}$$

(x) Similar to (ix).

□

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